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MICROWAVE HAIRPIN FILTER FOR 3.3GHz to 4.2 GHz

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ABSTRACT

The Design, measurements and simulations of Microwave Hairpin Filter are presented in this paper. Hairpin Filter is one of the most popular microwave filters because it is compact and does not require any grounding. It is designed at center frequency of 3.3 GHz to 4 GHz with a fractional bandwidth of 0.8 GHz with low insertion loss better than 10dB across the band. This frequency is presenting for WLAN Application. The design and simulation of hairpin filter is done by using ADS (Advanced Design System) software.

Keywords : ADS, WLAN, Microwave Hairpin Filter

I. INTRODUCTION

Micro strip band pass filters are essential high frequency components in microwave communication systems. Modern microwave communication system requires micro strip band pass filters[] with improved performance for out of band and in-band responses, low insertion loss, reduced size and high rejection. Parallel coupled micro strip filters are widely used in the RF Front end of microwave and wireless communication systems. The advantages of this filter are is planar structure, insensitivity to fabrication tolerances, reproducibility, wide range of filter fractional bandwidth and an easy design procedure [].

Parallel coupled micro strip filter with $\lambda/2$ resonators are common elements in many microwave systems, their large size is incompatible with the systems where size is an important consideration [3]. The length of parallel coupled filter is too long and it further increases with the order of the filter. To solve this problem, hairpin filter using folded $\lambda/2$ resonator structures were

developed [3] [6] . The traditional design of the hairpin topology has the advantage of compact structure, but it has limitation of wider bandwidth.

Conceptually they may be obtained by folding the resonators of parallel coupled, half wavelength resonator filter into a “U” shape. To fold resonators, it is necessary to consider the reduction for coupled-line lengths, which reduces the coupling between resonators.

The layout of the hairpin filter[1] is shown below.

Fig. 1 layout of hairpin filter

II. Initiation to Design

A full wave EM simulation is used for designing hairpin filter. For the design purpose the low pass prototype (Butterworth, cheybyshev and Bessel) is selected according to the design requirement. The equivalent circuit[1] of n-pole hairpin band pass filter is shown in fig.2

Fig.2 equivalent circuit of n-pole hairpin filter

As seen from fig.2 the equivalent circuit of n-pole hairpin filter, each resonator is modeled as a combination of inductor and capacitor. The mutual coupling co-efficient between two resonators is $M_{i,i+1}$, Q_{e1} and Q_{e2} are the quality factor at the input and output.

The coupling co-efficient[2] and quality factor can be calculated as

$$Q_{e1} = \frac{g_0 g_1}{FBW}$$

$$Q_{e2} = \frac{g_n g_{n+1}}{2a}$$

$$M_{i, i + 1} = \frac{FBW}{\sqrt{g_i g_{i+1}}} \quad \text{for } i = 1 \text{ to } n-1$$

Where FBW is the fractional bandwidth and $g_0, g_1, g_2, \dots, g_{n-1}$ are normalized low pass elements of the desired low pass filter approximation. The tapped position of the filter is calculated as

$$t = \frac{2L}{\pi} \sin^{-1} \left(\sqrt{\frac{\pi Z_0}{2Q_s Z_r}} \right)$$

Where Z_0 is the terminated impedance, Z_r is the characteristic impedance, Q_e is external quality factor and L is the arm length filter. The arm length of the filter can be calculated as

$$L = \frac{\lambda_g}{4}$$

$$\lambda_g = \frac{\lambda_0}{\sqrt{\epsilon_{re}}}$$

Where λ_0 is wavelength of the filter in vacuum, ϵ_{re} is effective dielectric constant of microstrip line.

The hairpin filter is a variant of the edge coupled band pass filter[1]. A sliding factor is introduced to allow for bending thus making the design more compact as shown below.

Fig.3. EDGE Coupled Filter

Fig.4. resonators are moved to provide slide angle

Fig.5. hairpin resonator structure

The structure which shown in fig (5), was observed large insertion loss and unacceptable return loss in FR4 laminates. A tapped hairpin filter has a smaller insertion loss and better return loss. This is a variant of an edge – coupled filter that contains matching stub. Varying the length of this stub and the tapping distance varies the return loss and consequently the insertion loss.

III. DESIGN AND SIMULATION

The filter must be able to operate between 3.7 GHz – 4.2 GHz and the filter response at 3.

The hairpin filter using ADS is done as shown in fig. The internal blocks of each section of fig are shown in the figure.

Fig.6. basic model of hairpin filter using ADS

Here instead of designing the whole filter we are dividing to total filter into two parts vertically. So we can see that both the parts of filter are identical but that are mirror image of each other through y-axis. So we are designing half of the filter and other part is obtained by mirror image of first part. By combining the sections we obtain our hairpin filter.

The first section of hair filter is shown in figure7

FIG.7. Design of hairpin filter using ADS

The block which are using in the design of filter are microstrip substrate , microstrip line, microstrip T- junction, optimally chamfered bend (90 degrees) , microstrip coupled lines are shown in fig.8-9

Fig.8 micro strip substrate

Fig.9 microstrip T, coupled line and bend

The effect of coupled lines along with capacitance and the response of this is shown in figure. Which is done using ADS.

Fig.10. coupled line section

Fig.11 response of coupled line section.

This figure (12) shows the complete implementation of the HAIRPIN filter using ADS software. This filter yields the output of a band pass filter which has a pass band from 3.7GHz to 4.2GHz.

Fig.12 implementation of hairpin filter using ADS

The response of hairpin band pass filter which has pass band from 3.3 – 4.0 GHz, is shown FIG. 13.

FIG. 14. Response of hairpin filter

IV. CONCLUSION

The microwave filters working in microwave frequency range of 0.3 GHz to 300 GHz which are made of lumped components are highly prone to damage due to continuous usage ground problem. Hence microstrip filters are used to overcome these problems. The hairpin filter which we designed is one this kind. It is proved to be effective for longer usage and it overcomes the grounding problem. Hence the hairpin filter design using ADS software is successful. By using ADS the passband of 0.8 GHz is obtained from the range of 3.3GHz to 4.0 GHz.

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